

PlagiarismSearch

Prepared by the PlagiarismSearch.com Team

Plagiarism Trends (2018–2024). Statistical Report by PlagiarismSearch.com

Based on the analysis of **69.89 million** plagiarism checks.
Data collected between January 2018 and December 2024

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Introduction

This report from the team of PlagiarismSearch presents a brief review of global trends in plagiarizing during a period covering seven full years **from 2018 up to the end 2024**. The data for the report has been drawn from **69.89 million** plagiarism checks that were performed on the PlagiarismSearch.com platform.

The input data for the analysis was collected from **anonymized document submissions** by students, educators, and institutions across different countries. All information used is aggregated and contains no personal identifiers.

The primary objective of this report is to track changes in plagiarism behavior over time and assess most influencing factors, including COVID-19 and the emergence of generative AI technologies, which determine plagiarism trends

This report is intended to support:

- academic institutions in refining academic integrity policies,
- researchers analyzing educational trends,
- policy and decision-makers in the education sector.

Summary of Key Finding

Year	Total Submissions	Avg Plagiarism Rate (%)	Δ vs previous year (%)
2018	4.2M	9.08	-
2019	5.8M	14.67	61.55
2020	7.2M	18.79	28.06
2021	10.3M	16.72	-11.01
2022	11.8M	15.25	-8.83
2023	13.9M	18.32	20.19
2024	16.7M	16.36	-10.72
Total	69.89M	-	-

Table 1. Annual Average Plagiarism Rate and Year-over-Year Change

The analyzed data clearly indicates the wave-like trends in instances of plagiarized submissions. A significant increase in plagiarism instances happened during 2019-2020, when the number of submissions containing plagiarized content increased by 61.55% and 28.06% respectively. Yet, those years mark the global shift to online mode of learning accepted by most educational institutions worldwide as a means to continue the educational processes in response to the lockdown caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

The following years, 2021 and 2022, the number of plagiarized submissions decreased by 11.01% and 8.83% respectively. That may indicate that educational institutions adapted to the new challenges of online learning environments and took measures to increase plagiarism awareness and maintain high academic integrity.

Yet continuing the wave-like pattern, instances of plagiarism in submissions rose again in 2023 by 20.19%, perfectly correlating with the mass adoption of generative AI tools, such as ChatGPT, and then resumed the downward trend in 2024 (-10.72%), possibly due to stricter AI-detection methods and academic integrity measures.

Average plagiarism rates in submissions vary from the minimum 9.08% recorded in 2018 to maximum 18.79% in 2020. However, the grand average rate of plagiarized content in submissions during the analyzed period is approximately 16.29%.

Plagiarism Trends (2018–2024)

Figure 1. Yearly Trend in Plagiarism Rates (with COVID and AI Zones Highlighted)

Factors that Affect Plagiarism Rates

The factors that influence the rates of using someone's ideas as well as rates of plagiarism in submissions can vary from social and psychological factors of individual students to technological and educational developments on the whole. Further we list the most vivid influencing factors that emerged between 2020 and 2024.

Shift to Remote Learning (2020–2021)

COVID-19 pandemic made the education sector to embrace online methods of education to support continuous learning processes. However, the abrupt transition to distant learning mode created numerous new challenges, especially in maintaining academic integrity. While students were attending classes remotely and submitting assignments online, educational institutions were unable to provide sufficient control mechanisms over student academic behaviors. Thus, the record-high plagiarism rates that were observed in 2019 and 2020 can be contributed to the lack of control mechanisms as well as absence of live supervision and in-person interaction.

Emergence of Generative AI Tools (2023–2024)

Easily available and accessible AI-based writing tools, particularly ChatGPT (released in late 2022), significantly changed the academic landscape. In 2023, many students began using generative AI to assist with or even fully complete written assignments, increasing the risk of unoriginal content. This technological shift likely explains the new spike in plagiarism detected that year.

Additional Influencing Factors

Other potential contributors include increased pressure to succeed, easy access to online sources and essay databases, and inconsistencies in online assessment procedures. Combined, these factors underscore the need for robust academic integrity policies and advanced detection tools.